

Assessment of morphological variations of the Inferior Alveolar Nerve Canal (IANC) using Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) amongst the North Indian population : a cross-sectional study

Received on : 24-10-2024 | Accepted on : 14-12-2024 | Published on : 10-03-2025

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Abstract

Background : Morphological variations of the inferior alveolar nerve canal (IANC) have been described in literature. It is important for the clinicians to recognize them and plan the treatment accordingly.

Aim: To assess morphological variations of the course of inferior alveolar nerve canal (IANC) using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) amongst the North Indian population.

Materials and methods : The study comprised of 100 CBCT scans which were performed for various dental procedures from the CBCT archives with the field of view (FOV) 10x5 cms or 10x10 cms. All scans were assessed for the morphological variations of the inferior alveolar nerve canal (IANC). Worthington's classification for categorization of single IANC, Langlais classification for categorization of bifid IANC and pictorial presentation given by Greenstein and Tarnow was used for the assessment of morphological variations. The scans were analysed by two examiners who had previously been trained as a specialist in oral and maxillofacial radiology.

Results : 100 CBCT scans were included where 53 were of females and 47 were of males with mean age of 47 years. The prevalence of single mandibular canal was 93% (n = 93). According to Worthington's classification the prevalence of single catenary type A was 54.83 % (n = 51), single progressive descending type B was 27.95% (n = 26) and single straight type C was 17.85% (n = 16). The total prevalence of bifid MC was 7% (n = 7), according to Langlais et al. the prevalence of bifid type 1 was 85.71% (n=6), type 2 was 0% (n = 0), type 3 was 0 (n = 0) and type 4 was 14.29% (n = 1). The prevalence of anterior extension amongst the single and bifid IANC was 15% (n=16). According to Greenstein and Tarnow the prevalence of anterior extension type A was 0 (n=0), anterior extension type B was 75.0 % (n=12) and type C was 25.0 % (n=4).

Conclusion : CBCT is suggested for a detailed evaluation and identification of inferior alveolar nerve canal before any surgical procedures to avoid post-operative complications.

Introduction

The Inferior Alveolar nerve canal (IANC) or the Mandibular canal (MC) is an imperative anatomical structure that extends bilaterally from the Mandibular foramen to the Mental foramen carrying the Inferior Alveolar nerve, artery and vein. The inferior alveolar nerve is a branch of the third division of the fifth cranial nerve which runs longitudinally along with the artery & vein throughout the spongy tissue of the bone in an antero-inferior direction and describe as a concave antero-superior curve.^[1] The IANC has been studied in detail since ages with respect to its location and path as well as the possible

variations in its normal anatomical course.^[2] (Figure.1) This important neurovascular bundle is responsible for the blood supply and sensory activity of the mandibular teeth, lower lip, adjacent alveolar bone and gingiva. Radiographically, the MC is observed as a dark linear shadow between two thin, radio-opaque lines (one superior and the other inferior) projected on the bone, which limits the canal. (Figure.2)

How to Cite This Article : Kumar et al. - Assessment of Morphological Variations of The Inferior Alveolar Nerve Canal (IANC) Using Cone Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) Amongst The North Indian Population: A Cross-sectional Study, AJOADUD 2025

Figure 1: The inferior alveolar nerve (IAN) canal^[3]

Figure 2: IANC marked bilaterally on reconstructed panoramic image using nerve marking tool

Anthropological study done by Chavez et al. suggested that during embryonic development there are three different inferior alveolar nerves which innervate three different areas of the hemi-mandible (antero-inferior teeth, primary molars and permanent molars), which finally fuse to form a single nerve. Authors suggested that incomplete fusion of these three nerve branches results in the appearance of a bifid or trifid MC.

Many authors have come up with categorization of the canal as per its topography or usual course and also tried to include the variations (if any) in its path both clinically as well as radiographically.

Acquaintance of dentists with the topography of the inferior alveolar nerve canal is essential for various surgical procedures including dental implant placement, third molar surgery, dental anaesthesia, mandibular osteotomy, bone harvesting procedure from the ramus and body of mandible, bone plating in angle and body region of mandible, or any other surgical procedure involving the mandible to avoid inadvertent injury to inferior alveolar nerve (IAN). It has been reported that IAN damage may cause sensory deficits up to 8.3% to 77.8%, depending on the type of surgery.^[5]

Until the advent of CBCT, the panoramic radiographs were used to identify the morphological variations in the mandibular canals. Several studies done using orthopantomogram have shown lower prevalence of IANC variations when compared with CBCT, attributed to the lack of information provided in two-dimensional view.

Radiographic assessment of the inferior alveolar nerve canal (IANC)

The radiographic appearance of mandibular canal has been described as a “radiolucent dark ribbon between two white lines” by Worth.^[6] White & Pharaoh defined it as “dark linear shadow with thin radiopaque superior and inferior borders cast by the lamella of bone that bounds the canal”. It

occasionally duplicates in mediolateral directions as bifurcation and even as trifurcation.^[7]

Genetic variations amongst different populations could be the cause behind the morphologic variation in the anatomical landmarks. Morphological variations are responsible for various complications during dental procedures which can be handled by the clinicians if they have sound knowledge about various anatomical landmarks and their variations.

The purpose of this study was to assess the morphological variations of the inferior alveolar nerve canal using CBCT in North Indian population.

Materials & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, ITS Dental College, Greater Noida, to assess the prevalence of morphological variations of the inferior alveolar nerve canal (IANC) in North Indian population. 100 CBCT scans were randomly selected from the archives which were performed from June 2022 to December 2023. Scans of patient from North India with radiographically evident corticated inferior alveolar nerve canal with age above 18 with known gender were included. Scans with evidence of fractures, pathological lesions, orthognathic surgery involving the mandible were not included in the study.

Image Evaluation Using CBCT

All CBCT scans were reformatted using CS3D viewer software on LED 19”5' inch monitor screen with 1600 × 900 pixels resolution under dim light condition using the nerve marking tool, the course of the inferior alveolar nerve was traced using orange colour. The tracing was done in the panoramic view which can be viewed in the axial, coronal, and cross-sectional views. Evaluation and analysis of the morphological variations was performed by two examiners trained in the field of oral & maxillofacial radiology at specific interval of time. Worthington's classification was used for the categorization of single IANC while the classification system given by Langlai's et al was used for the assessment of bifid canals. Pictorial presentation given by Greenstein and Tarnow was followed for the evaluation of anterior extension of IANC.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed using SPSS software (SPSS version 27.0, SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Categorical data was analyzed for differences between groups based on gender, side, and canal type using the Chi square test. and interobserver reliability was determined using Cohen's kappa coefficient. McNemar's test compared the prevalence of mandibular anatomical variations in 100 CBCT scans. The kappa coefficient to calculate the agreement between the observer 1 and observer 2 was 99% with the significance level set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

The age range of the individuals whose scans were assessed was within the range of 18-86 years.

Out of 100 CBCT scans, 62% were of right side of the mandible and 38% were of left side of the mandible. The total

prevalence of single mandibular canal was 93% (n = 93) while that of the bifid mandibular canal was 7% (n=7) (Table-2).

TYPE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SINGLE	93	93
BIFID	7	7
TOTAL	100	100

Table 2: Prevalence of the different types of MC.

According to Worthington's^[8] classification the prevalence of single catenary type 1A was 54.83 % (n = 51), single progressive descending type 1B was 27.95% (n = 26) single straight type 1C was 17.85% (n = 16). (Graph 1) There was no significant difference appreciated with the age (p = 0.750) and gender (p=0.760). (Graph 1)

Graph 1: Prevalence of different types of single MC

The total prevalence of bifid MC was 7% (n=7), according to Langlais et al.^[9] classification the prevalence of type 1 bifid MC was 85.71% (n=6), type 2 was 0% (n = 0), type 3 was 0 (n = 0) and type 4 was 14.28% (n = 1). (Graph 1) However, for each type of bifid MC, there was no statistically significant differences was found with the age (p= 0.136) and gender (p=0.069).

Graph 2: Prevalence of different types of bifid MC.

The prevalence of anterior extension amongst single and bifid IANC was 16% (n=16). According to Greenstein and Tarnow^[10] the prevalence of anterior extension type A was 0 (n=0), type B was 75.0 % (n=12) and type C was 25.0 % (n=4). (Graph 3) There were no statistically significant

differences found between the age (p = 0.371) and gender (p =0.750.) respectively.

Graph 3: Prevalence of different types of anterior extension of MC.

Discussion

In the past, the studies aimed to assess the inferior alveolar nerve canal and its variants, were limited to gross evaluation on cadavers, dry skulls and the radiographic assessment using 2D imaging modalities like orthopantomogram.^[3,11,12] Studies using CBCT for the evaluation of the MC represent a relatively pertinent area of research. Increased interest in this subject has been driven by greater frequency of placement of endosseous dental implants, advanced orthognathic surgeries, and the need to avoid morbidity associated with IAN injury during surgical procedures.

In the present study, the prevalence of single mandibular canal was found to be 93% (n=93) while bifid mandibular canal had a prevalence of only 7% (n=7). Nithya et al. conducted a similar study on 203 CBCT images out of which 21 images showed the presence of bifid mandibular canals indicating the prevalence of the of bifid canal as 10.3%.^[13] Fuentes R et al. in his study on Chilean population, using digital panoramic radiography, reported the overall prevalence of bifid MC to be 11% (n = 102).^[11] Anthropological study done by Chavez et al. suggested that during embryologic development three different mandibular canals occurred in each hemi mandible. Thereafter, from each canal three different inferior dental nerves originate and innervates the three mandibular regions. During prenatal growth phase of bone remodeling and apposition, these three canals eventually fuse to form a single canal. Incomplete fusion of these three canals may result in anatomical variations such as bifurcation or trifurcation.^[4]

Worthington's classification for the categorization of the configuration of single IANC has been considered in the present study, according to which IANC can have three basic configurations i.e. Type 1 (catenary), 2 (progressive descending) and 3 (straight). Catenary type was most commonly observed with a prevalence of 54.83% (n =51), followed by single progressive descending type with a prevalence of 27.95 % (n = 26) and then straight type with a prevalence of 17.20% (n = 16). Unlike our study, a study conducted by Mirbeigi et al.,evaluated the course of IANC amongst the Iranian population using CBCT and reported an equal distribution (n=52) of three different categories of IANC.^[14] Andrew Okiriamu et al.

evaluated the course of IANC amongst the Kenyan population using CBCT and found progressive descending type in 241 (68.7%) scans, catenary type in 77 (21.9%) scans, and the straight type in 33 (9.4%) scans.^[12] Ozturk's et al. evaluated the pattern of IANC on dry skulls of USA population using CBCT and observed catenary type in almost one-half (51.1%) of the specimens, followed by the progressive descending (36.7%) and then straight type (12.2%).^[15] Therefore, as observed demographic variations can be attributed as the reason behind catenary being the most prevalent type.

After observing the prevalence rate of the bifid canal, the present study applied Langlais et al. classification for categorization of the course of bifid IANC. According to which the bifid canals can be categorised into 4 types with further subtypes.^[9] Our study observed the prevalence of further subtypes such as Type I as 85.71% (n = 6), type II as 0% (n = 0), type III as 14.28% (n = 1) and type IV as 0% (n = 0). Following the same classification Komal et al. conducted a study of normal anatomy of mandibular canal and its variations in Indian population using CBCT. They observed only 1% prevalence of bifid mandibular canal which was Type 2 in nature.^[16]

In its first of a kind study to know the prevalence of bifid mandibular canal, conducted by R P . Langlais, R Broadus, B J Glasson 6000 panoramic radiographs, prevalence of bifid MC was found to be 0.95%, with type II being the most frequent variant. The prevalence rate of type II was reported as 54.4% followed by type I with the prevalence of 38.6%. Type III & Type IV had equal prevalence of 3.5%.^[10]

Fuentes R, et al. applied the same classification system on Chilean population using digital panoramic radiography and reported the prevalence of Type I bifid MC as 7.4% (n = 69), type II as 2.3% (n = 23), type III as 0% (n = 0) and type IV as 1.1% (n = 10).^[11] Another study by Kalantar Motamedi et al. conducted on 5000 panoramic radiographs reported the most frequently encountered type of bifid canal as type 2 (82%).^[17] Hass LF et al. suggested that CBCT showed a higher prevalence of variations in mandibular canal (16.25%) when compared to panoramic radiography (6.46%).^[18]

The previous studies reported that the prevalence of bifid mandibular canal identified using CBCT was higher than that obtained using panoramic radiographs. Tantanapornkul et al. compared panoramic radiographs and CBCT in the detection of mandibular canal and reported that CBCT had 93% of sensitivity and 77% of specificity.^[19] They concluded that CBCT can be used for more accurate visualization of mandibular nerve. Neves et al. assessed the presence of bifid mandibular canal using panoramic radiograph and CBCT. They reported 2.4% higher prevalence of bifid mandibular canal when observed through CBCT.^[20] Therefore, the present study used CBCT for visualization of inferior alveolar nerve canal.

In the present study overall prevalence of anterior exten-

sion amongst the single and bifid MC was found to be 16% (n=16). Gupta A et al. reported a prevalence rate of 56.0% of anterior loop in a total sample of 600 CBCT scans while Puri et al. found the prevalence rate of 53.13%, in a total sample of 5 CBCT scans done in a pilot study, on the West Indian population.^[21,22] On the contrary a study carried out by Sinha et al. in East Indian population found that the prevalence rate of anterior loop was only 9.7% on CBCT images.^[23] Further more Kajan and Salari reported the prevalence of 36.9% anterior loop amongst the Iranian population in his study conducted in 2012 using CBCT.^[24] Also, De Oliveira- Santos et al. reported an overall prevalence rate of 22%– 28% of the anterior loop in 100 CBCT scans.^[25] On a study conducted on panoramic radiographs, Ngeow et al. reported 40.2% of anterior loop on panoramic radiographs.^[26]

Nina and Stoltze suggested that the visibility of anterior loop reduces as the age of the subjects increased. The difficulty in visualizing the anterior loop in older subjects may be a result of reduced calcification of the cortex which happens with age progression.^[27]

Greenstein and Tarnow in their review gave a pictorial representation of different types of anterior extension of inferior alveolar nerve canal.^[10] In this present study we applied the same pictorial representation for knowing the prevalence of anterior extension types. The prevalence of anterior extension type A was 0.0% (n=0), type B was 75.0% (n=12) and type C was 25.0% (n=4). It was found that type B was the most common followed by type C and then type A.

The limitation of the present study is that of a small sample size. The variation in the pattern of morphological types of IANC could be attributed to the differences in the study sample size, and the varied population groups. Studies on larger sample size in diverse population needs to be done to draw a definite conclusion.

Conclusion

CBCT provides an effective tool for presurgical evaluation of the neurovascular structures and its variations. This knowledge is pertinent in the preoperative assessment and planning of surgeries. This information shall be helpful in avoidance of iatrogenic injuries which tend to occur during the surgical procedures in the maxillofacial region.

We conclude that CBCT is suggested for a detailed evaluation to avoid post-operative complications and contribute to the provision of safe and effective dental care, ultimately enhancing the patient's experience.

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